

ReCreate

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Räsänen et al.

Properties and quality of precast concrete elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots

Publisher / project	Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy
Project acronym	ReCreate
Deliverable	D4.2 Properties and quality of deconstructed precast concrete elements in pilot projects
Lead beneficiary	Tampere University (TAU)
Author(s)	Räsänen, A. (TAU), Lahdensivu, J. (TAU), Gudmundsson, K. (KTH), Dervishaj, A. (KTH), Westerlind, H. (KTH), Lambrechts, T., Vullings, M. (TU/e), Arnold, V. (BTU) & Huuhka, S. (TAU)
Dissemination level	Public
Cite this document	Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Lambrechts, T., Vullings, M., Arnold, V. & Huuhka, S. (2024). <i>Properties and quality of precast concrete elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots</i> . The ReCreate project.
Disclaimer	The content presented herein reflect the authors' views. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.

Abstract

A process for ensuring the properties of deconstructed precast concrete elements is essential for safe reuse. The properties are important for structural designers when designing a new building with reused elements and evaluating their structural capacity and service-life.

The ReCreate project researches the process of reusing precast concrete elements through four real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots in Europe. The aim is to study different aspects of the whole process, including quality assurance.

To reuse precast concrete elements safely, it is essential to ensure their material properties. Especially when reusing load-bearing structures, certain properties, such as compressive strength, reinforcement details and cover depth of reinforcement, are required for evaluating structural capacity. However, the requirements for testing depend on the requirements of the new application, as the durability requirements may be different in different applications.

This document describes the tests done in each of ReCreate's four real-life pilots in the different countries (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany).

Acknowledgements

The following ReCreate team members provided background information on the ReCreate deconstruction pilots used in the writing of this report: Jani Mikkola and Guy Rapaport (Ramboll Finland), Janne Hakala, Hannu Rannanjärvi, Tommi Heikkinen and Juha Rämö (Consolis Parma), Tero Niemelä (Skanska), Eric Rawlins (LIKE Architects), Erik Stenberg, Jose Hernandez Vargas and Ahmad Al-Najjar (KTH), Henrik Vinell (Consolis Strängbetong), Christine Delander Eksten, Tina Appelqvist and Caroline Wedelsbäck (Helsingborgshem), Marijn Landman (IMd), Justin Houtman (Lagemaat), Angelika Mettke, Jakob Fischer and Christoph Henschel (BTU), and Peter Jähne (P. Jähne Ingenieurbüro).

Contents

1.	Introduction.....	1
2.	Finland.....	3
2.1.	Donor building	3
2.2.	In-situ investigation.....	5
2.3.	Laboratory tests.....	6
2.4.	Results	9
3.	Sweden.....	14
3.1.	Donor building	14
3.2.	In-situ investigation.....	18
3.3.	Laboratory tests.....	19
3.4.	Results	20
4.	The Netherlands.....	25
4.1.	Donor building	25
4.2.	In-situ investigation.....	27
4.3.	Laboratory tests.....	28
4.4.	Results	30
5.	Germany.....	32
5.1.	Donor building	32
5.2.	In-situ investigation.....	33
5.3.	Laboratory tests & structural analysis.....	35
5.4.	Results	37
6.	Conclusions.....	41
	References.....	42

1. Introduction

The ReCreate project researches the reusability of precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, with four deconstruction and reuse pilot projects located in Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany. The deconstruction pilots are described in detail Vullings et al. (2024). The current report focuses on the deconstructed elements' quality assurance in each of the pilots, i.e. the tests done to ensure the material properties and quality of the elements reclaimed in the pilots. The whole procedure for quality management will be discussed in an upcoming ReCreate Deliverable D4.1., and the project's recommendations for a best practice will be given in a future Deliverable 4.3.

One of the most essential stages in the quality assurance process in preparation for reuse in new construction is ensuring the material properties and quality of the reclaimed elements. These are directly connected to structural safety, so reliable information is needed for safe reuse. The information can be gathered from original design documents and/or by doing tests on the elements. However, the extent of tests and required information depend on the properties of the elements and demands of the new building. The properties may vary between different element types and therefore each element type need to be evaluated separately. In addition, the properties in elements may vary between the same element type, and hence the reliability of the information depends on the reliability of the tests. Also, the new building may set new requirements for the properties, as the standards for designing concrete structures (currently EN 1990 [2023], EN 1991 [2002] and EN 1992 [2023]) may have been updated from the time when the elements were originally manufactured. Therefore, the requirements of information for ensuring material properties and quality needs to be individually evaluated in each case.

Structural safety of precast reinforced concrete (RC) elements as well as for prestressed concrete elements (in this case hollow-core slabs) can be ensured by calculating the structural capacity and evaluating the remaining service-life. To calculate the structural capacity of RC structures according to Eurocodes EN 1990 (2023), EN 1991 (2002) and EN 1992 (2023), compressive strength of concrete, cover depth of reinforcement and strength of reinforcement are needed. Therefore, these are the essential properties to ensure in the first place.

The method for evaluating the compressive strength is described in the European standard EN 13791:2019 (2019), and the method for testing the strength of reinforcement is described in the international standard ISO 6892-1:2019 (2019). There may also be national standards which may be used instead. The method for measuring the cover depth is not described in European standards but is established in practice. However, these properties can also be found from original design documents, in which case testing may not be needed.

In addition to the requirements for structural capacity, according to Eurocode EN 1992 (2023) the exposure class needs to be set for structures to ensure durability and service-life. The exposure classes are divided into seven different categories and 21 classes according to different environments and factors affecting durability. The classes set

requirements for cracking width, cover depth and resistance for freezing and thawing, chemical and mechanical exposure. Therefore, which properties need to be ensured varies for different exposure classes and must be considered individually, depending on the new use of a reclaimed element.

There may also be national regulations regarding hazardous and toxic substances, which need to be investigated. The presence of hazardous and toxic substances depends on the building, as different materials have been used in different eras. In addition, hazardous and toxic substances may be present in coatings and joints of elements, and thus the elements may need to be tested for them. Therefore, hazardous and toxic substances must also be considered individually.

Next, it is described how the mentioned properties and substances were studied in ReCreate's pilot projects in Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany.

2. Finland

2.1. Donor building

The Finnish donor building was an office building built in Tampere in 1982. Thus, it was 41 years in service before the deconstruction. The building consisted of two wings, one with seven floors and the other with one floor (Figure 2). The precast elements from the seven-floor wing were deconstructed for reuse, while the one-floor wing was demolished conventionally. The load-bearing frame of the building consisted of precast columns, beams and hollow-core slabs. These elements were salvaged for reuse. In addition, the precast sandwich elements in the building's short facades were load-bearing elements as well. The whole building was braced with two in-situ cast elevator shafts.

Figure 1. Finnish donor building. Photo © TAU/Heikki Vuorinen.

The load-bearing elements deconstructed for reuse were originally designed for indoor conditions. Therefore, the elements are only suitable for indoor environment, as the Nordic climate conditions are severe in Finland and require e.g., freeze-thaw resistance from outdoor structures exposed to wetting. If elements designed for indoor conditions were to be reused outdoors, additional refurbishment would be required, e.g. protective structures or layers would be needed to prevent wetting, freezing and thawing.

Structural design values are available from original design documents and technical drawings for beams and columns (Figure 2 and Figure 3). The original documents include measurements of elements; size, amount, location and strength of the reinforcement; and compressive strength of concrete. The technical drawings for hollow-core slabs were not available as they had gone missing from the archives, but a list of hollow-core slabs with original design values was found. The properties from the original documents were ensured with in-situ and laboratory testing as described in Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

Figure 2. Original detail drawing of precast concrete beam (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 3. Original detail drawing of precast concrete column (source: City of Tampere archives).

According to the original technical documents, compressive strength class of concrete in the columns and beams is K 30-2, which equals the compressive strength class C25/30 in the current Eurocode 2 EN 1992 (2023). The grade of reinforcement steel is A400H, which is no more in use in new construction. Nowadays, the most common strength for reinforcement in Finland is 500 MPa, which differs from A400H in its properties. However, the design values of the steel grade A400H are known, and the capacity of the elements can be calculated according to the properties in the original technical documents. The yield strength of the reinforcement steel is 400 MPa. A diameter of the main reinforcement in the columns and beams is the same, 20 mm. Tie reinforcements in columns are 6 mm and stirrups in beams are 8 mm. The design value of tension in the strands in hollow-core slabs is 900 MN/m².

2.2. In-situ investigation

The elements in the Finnish donor building were investigated in-situ before the deconstruction. The building was still in use while the in-situ investigation was conducted, which was considered in the planning of the investigation. The sample sizes, sampling spots, test methods and studied elements were selected based on a visual in-situ investigation and the original documents. The in-situ investigation included studying the structural properties of the elements and sampling for the laboratory tests.

The structural in-situ investigation included testing of cover depth of reinforcement, uniformity of the beams and columns, and sampling for surveying hazardous and toxic substances and testing compressive strength and carbonation depth in laboratory. The cover depth of reinforcement was measured from the hollow-core slabs as well, but other tests were not performed on hollow-core slabs while the building was in use. The sampling for compressive strength test for hollow-core slabs was done later, in a laboratory.

Measurements

The dimensions of the elements were obtained from original drawings, and a BIM model was created. To verify the dimensions, one storey of the building was 3D laser scanned, turned into a point cloud and used to verify that the built building's dimensions match those given in the original drawings.

Cover depth of reinforcement

The concrete cover depth was measured from each reinforcement type of the columns, beams and hollow-core slabs. Test was done by using a Proceq Profometer PM-650 device, which is a non-destructive test method. Each reading was taken from randomly selected elements. A total number of measurements for each element and reinforcement type are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The number of measurements for each element and reinforcement type.

Element type	Reinforcement type	Number of measurements
Beams	Main	454
	Stirrup	604
Columns	Main	564
	Tie	665
Hollow-core slabs	Strand	108

Uniformity

Uniformity of the beams and columns was tested by using a portable ultrasonic tomograph device, A1040 MIRA (Figure 4). The testing was done for the same randomly selected elements as in other tests. Sample size for the test was 6 for columns and 8 for beams.

Figure 4. Uniformity testing with non-destructive MIRA device. Photo © TAU/Aapo Räsänen.

2.3. Laboratory tests

Laboratory tests include testing and analysing of the samples taken in the in-situ investigation. Samples were taken for testing compressive strength, carbonation depth and hazardous and toxic substances. In addition, laboratory tests include load tests for deconstructed elements and freeze-thaw resistance for the hollow-core slabs.

Compressive strength

The sampling, examining, and testing to assess the compressive strength was done according to EN 12504-1:2019 + AC:2020 (2021). Core samples were drilled from the elements with a diamond drill; the diameter of the cores was 75 mm. The total number of cores extracted was 30: 15 were taken from the columns and 15 from the beams. The samples were taken randomly from different spots of the building (Figure 5). The samples from the individual elements were taken from spots avoiding reinforcement and critical areas as compression zone in beams. The characteristic compressive strength was then calculated from the compressive strength test results according to European standard EN 13791:2019 (2019) and Finnish national application standard SFS 7508:2021 (2021), which considers the size of the core with a national size impact factor.

In addition to the core testing, rebound hammer test was done to evaluate the compressive strength as well. The test was done according to EN 12504-2:2021 (2021) and Finnish national application standard SFS 7508:2021 (2021). A total of 15 readings from 8 columns and 9 beams were taken. The elements were the same as in the core test. The compressive strength was then calculated according to the SFS 7508:2021 (2021).

Figure 5. Investigation plan for drilling cores (source: investigation plan, Jani Mikkola Ramboll Finland).

Carbonation depth

Carbonation depth was measured from beams and columns according to RILEM CPC-18 (1988). Measurements were taken from the core samples before compressive strength testing by using phenolphthalein liquid as an indicator. The carbonation depth was also measured from 5 separate core samples from columns. The diameter of the cores was 50 mm, and the carbonation depth was measured by petrographic examination of thin sections according to standard ASTM C856/C856M-20 (2020).

Hazardous substances

Hazardous substances were studied from the building according to Finnish national guideline RT 103501 (2022). The guideline considers asbestos, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyl compounds (PCBs), lead, heavy metals, and petroleum hydrocarbons. Each material and element were evaluated, and the samples were taken from randomly selected spots which were identified as potentially containing hazardous or toxic substances. A total of 15 samples were taken, 8 from the seven-floor wing and 7 from the one-floor wing. In addition to the Finnish national guideline, total volatile organic compounds (TVOC) and 2-Ethylhexanol compound were studied from the screeding and top surface of the hollow-core slabs of the seven-floor wing with 8 samples.

Load tests

All deconstructed element types, i.e. beams, columns and hollow-core slabs, will be load tested (Table 2). The load tests will be done to study the failure strength, but also to ensure the reliability of the properties gotten from original documents and in-situ investigation. For hollow-core slabs, it is also for ensuring the compressive strength of the concrete, as it was not investigated before. The results will also be used together with other test results in the design process of the new building. In addition, the reinforcement of the elements will be tested for tensile strength.

Table 2. Dimensions of the salvaged elements.

Element type	Length [mm]	Height [mm]	Width [mm]
Beams	6400 and 4800	440	400
Columns	2800	400	400
Hollow-core slabs	~4750	200	1200

The hollow-core slabs were load tested for shear resistance according to European product standard EN 1168 + A3 (2012). Compressive strength of the hollow-core slabs was evaluated from the cores taken from the slabs. It was also used in the planning of the load test. Three cores were taken from each slab, and the average value of these was used. Two types of hollow-core slabs were used in the building: one with 4 pre-stressed strands and the other with 7 pre-stressed strands. A total of 6 hollow-core slabs were load tested, 3 of each type. The elements were randomly selected from two different floors.

The beams and columns for load test were also selected randomly. Additionally, two beams were specially selected, because they exhibited inconsistencies in the uniformity test. The load tests for columns and beams will be conducted during spring 2024. A total of 6 beams and 6 columns will be tested for bending strength. In addition, 4 hollow-core slabs will be tested to study remaining tension in the strands.

Protective pore ratio

Freeze-thaw resistance of the hollow-core slabs was evaluated by studying protective pore ratio according to SFS 4475 (1988). Their deconstruction took partly place during early winter, subjecting the elements to freezing and thawing. In addition, the elements are covered and stored outdoors (Figure 6), but they were not dried ahead of storage and can thus be exposed to freezing and thawing. However, the cover will prevent wetting during late winter, and thus reduce the cycles of freezing and thawing. A total of 10 samples were tested from 5 different piece of 2 hollow-core slabs, two samples from each piece.

Figure 6. Covered elements in storage. Photo © TAU/Aapo Räsänen.

2.4. Results

Visual inspection

Elements were evaluated visually during the in-situ investigation. No damage or deflections were detected, and the quality of the elements was evaluated to be high. In addition, visual evaluation was done during and after deconstruction. A guideline for evaluating significant damage or deflections was created for site to reject structurally deficient elements. Minor deflections will be evaluated in more detail before refurbishment at element factory.

Cover depth

The cover depth measurements vary between the elements (Table 3). However, mean value of the measurements for each element type is sufficient for indoor elements for service-life of 100 years according to EN 1992 (2023).

In addition, the cover depth is required for calculating the fire resistance of the elements. The fire resistance requirements depend on the requirements of the new building, so the adequacy of cover depth still needs to be ensured in the design process. If it is not sufficient, repair measures should be conducted.

Table 3. Mean value of the cover depth measurements.

Element type	Reinforcement type	Mean value [mm]
Beams	Main	38.2
	Tie	26.9
Columns	Main	34.2
	Stirrup	31.4
Hollow-core slabs	Strand	35.4

Uniformity

Uniformity of the concrete in beams and columns is mostly high (Figure 7). Doubtful results were gotten from two beams on the sixth floor, and the doubtful areas are relatively small. In both beams, the areas are local in the most reinforced sections, as there is dense tie reinforcement as well as reinforcement for a hole and lifting. Hence, there may be a small lack of compactness in the concrete. These beams will be investigated more closely and load tested in laboratory. However, these defects are not expected to significantly reduce the structural capacity.

Figure 7. Ultrasonic tomography results. Normal findings (left) and anomalous findings (right) (source: report of reusability assessment, Guy Rapaport Ramboll Finland).

Compressive strength

Characteristic compressive strength calculated from core samples is 40 MPa for the beams and 47 MPa for the columns. The evaluated characteristic compressive strength values are significantly higher than the original designed compressive strength 25 MPa (C25/30) given in the technical drawings. Therefore, a higher compressive strength may be used instead of the original design value.

For hollow-core slabs, the compressive strength was evaluated from the mean values of the cores taken in load test. The mean values of three core samples from each load tested slabs are between 76 and 80 MPa, which are also significantly higher than expected. The

compressive strength class of hollow-core slabs is usually C50/60 in new products. The characteristic value was not calculated, as the exact compressive strength value is needed for load tests. In addition, the structural capacity is evaluated from the results of the load tests, and hence the characteristic compressive strength value is not needed.

The original compressive strength class was also evaluated with rebound hammer. For beams and columns, the calculated median values exceeded the required values for the original compressive strength class C25/30. For the hollow-core slabs, the evaluated compressive strength class acquired through the rebound hammer test was C50/60.

Carbonation depth

Carbonation depths in beams and columns are relatively small (Table 4), and the carbonation front has not reached the reinforcement. Therefore, no risk for corrosion currently exists, and no further investigation is needed. However, the possibility of the corrosion needs to be evaluated in the new building, as the environment may be different from the donor building. If the environment is suitable for corrosion to occur, further investigation and calculations may be needed. The results from phenolphthalein indicator and thin section analysis are similar to one other.

Table 4. Carbonation depth measurements.

Element type	Range of carbonation depth measurements [mm]	Mean value using phenolphthalein indicator [mm]	Mean value using petrographic examination [mm]
Beams	0-5	1.2	-
Columns	0-8	0.8	1.4

Hazardous and toxic substances

No hazardous or toxic substances were found in the salvaged elements (Table 5). Individual high content values were observed in the screed topping the hollow-core slabs, but not in the slabs themselves. The screed was therefore removed before deconstruction, as a part of the internal stripping.

Table 5. Hazardous substance findings.

Hazardous substance	Content
Asbestos	0
PAH	0
PCB	0
Lead	0
TVOC (Hollow-core slabs)	
Screed	10-120 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{h}$]
Concrete	<10 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{h}$]
2-Ethylhexanol (Hollow-core slabs)	
Screed	4-81 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{h}$]
Concrete	2-11 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{h}$]

Load tests

The results of the load test for hollow-core slabs were as expected (Table 6). Calculations made according to the tested compressive strength and original technical documents correlate with the ultimate loads observed in the load tests. Thereby the hollow-core slabs can be re-designed using existing standards and the test results.

Table 6. Results of the load test of hollow-core slabs.

Hollow-core slab type	Number of slabs tested	Calculated strength [kN]	Ultimate load [kN]
4AX (4 strands)	3	72-76	86-103
7X (7 strands)	3	102-103	126-168

Protective pore ratio

Variable protective pore ratios of the hollow-core slabs were partly expected (Table 7), as elements intended for indoor conditions are not manufactured to contain protective pores. The ratios are outside of the recommendations for normal strength freeze-thaw resistant concrete. The declaration of the protective pore ratio has not been a practice since 2004, but the recommendation for freeze-thaw resistance concrete used to be 0.20. However, as the compressive strength in the hollow-core slabs is high (76-80 MPa), the recommended protective pore ratio value can be lower than for normal strength concrete, and still be sufficient. Therefore, the strength is high enough for freeze-thaw resistance. In addition, the elements are covered from rain and sleet during storage.

Table 7. Protective pore ratios for samples taken from hollow-core slabs.

Sample	Protective pore ratio
1	0.09
2	0.14
3	0.21
4	0.12
5	0.12

3. Sweden

3.1. Donor building

The elements reused in ReCreate's Swedish reuse pilot, which was a temporary exhibition pavilion for the H22 city expo in Helsingborg, originated from two deconstructed buildings in Helsingborg, Drottninghög and Huggjärnet. The hollow-core slabs used in the pilot were factory rejects from Strängbetong. In addition, the slab-on-ground originated from the previous building that stood on the plot on which the pilot was built.

Donor building in Drottninghög

The two pieces of wall elements and a floor element were reused from a block of flats that stood in 'Drottninghög Västra 1' area, built in the period of 1967-69 (Figure 8). The building had three floors with a cross-wall structure: transverse load-bearing internal walls perpendicular to the lateral axis of the building (Figure 9).

Figure 8. The donor building in Drottninghög (source: Helsingborgshem).

The reused elements are originally from indoors, so they have not been designed for outdoor exposure. Both wall and floor elements were reused. The original drawings were available for the elements, and hence the properties, such as compressive strength, measurements, location and strength of the reinforcement could be identified (Figure 10).

Figure 9. First floor plan of the donor building, showing the placement of elements (source: Municipality of Helsingborg).

Figure 10. Drawing of wall element V7D and floor element P2 that were used in the Swedish reuse pilot (source: Municipality of Helsingborg).

The concrete used in the elements is of class BTG II STD K250, which corresponds to a class of C25/30 (BTG II STD K200 in Foundation) in Eurocode 2 EN 1992 (2023). The used reinforcement grade KS40 corresponds to the current steel grade B500BT (KS, i.e. *kamstång*, refers to a ribbed bar). However, further investigations were done to ensure the original values, as described in Sections 4.2 and 4.3.

Donor building in Huggjärnet

The columns and beams reused in the Swedish pilot were originally from an industrial building 'Huggjärnet 13' close to Drottninghög in Helsingborg. Huggjärnet 13 had a load-bearing concrete column and beam frame built in 1966 (Figure 11 and Figure 12), and the elements were not originally exposed to outdoor environment.

The original design values were identified from the available original drawings. The drawings included amount, location and strength of the reinforcement, and strength class of concrete (Figure 11). The concrete class is K500 (kp/cm²) and the strength class of reinforcement is KS60 according to the drawings. The location of the reinforcement was ensured by destructive methods.

Figure 12. The industrial building, including the columns that were reused (left) and inspection of rebar through destructive testing (right) (source: Helsingborgshem).

Slab-on-ground from a demolished pre-school building

The Swedish reuse pilot was built on top of an existing concrete slab originating from a demolished pre-school building. The structural properties of the slab were investigated through the inspection of original drawings. However, the relatively thin slab called for special precautions when it came to the placement of columns of the pilot building. The reused on-site slab element is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. The retained concrete slab of the pre-school, on top of which the Swedish reuse pilot was built (source: Helsingborgshem).

Factory rejects

The hollow-core slabs are factory rejects from Strängbetong. The structural properties were obtained from documentation provided by the manufacturer. The reason for rejecting prefabricated elements at the factory is that they do not fulfil the client specific requirements regarding dimensions or load-bearing capacity.

3.2. In-situ investigation

Assessing the durability of concrete elements for reuse is necessary. Their durability can be affected by corrosion of steel rebars, which can cause cracking and spalling of concrete. Corrosion can be caused by factors, such as carbonation (lowering the pH of concrete) and chloride ingress through diffusion. While the structural elements are located indoors, and not direct contact with seawater or de-icing salts, corrosion risks were considered in the following investigations. In-situ investigation of the deconstructed elements from Drottninghög included measurements of carbonation depth, cover depth of reinforcement, sampling for surveying hazardous and toxic substances, and testing compressive strength of concrete. In addition, the cover depth and the carbonation depth were measured from an existing reference building belonging to the same building stock (another building along the same street).

The elements from other sources were not investigated in-situ, but the properties were acquired from original design documents.

Cover depth of reinforcement

Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) was used to scan one apartment in the reference building. A portable concrete GPR Proceq GP8800 was used. The radar has a high frequency antenna, and it can perform 2 scans/cm. The data was used to estimate the cover depth of reinforcement and the spacing between reinforcement, but cannot be used to accurately predict the diameter of rebars.

Carbonation depth

Carbonation depth was measured in-situ by applying the Swedish national standard SS 137242:1988 (1988). An indicator liquid was sprayed on just-sawn concrete surface, and the liquid changes the colour of an uncarbonated area. However, the used indicator liquid was different from the liquid mentioned in the standard. The used indicator liquid consisted of 1% thymolphthalein dissolved in ethanol, which changes the colour of the uncarbonated concrete to blue. One core from a deconstructed wall and two cores from a slab element were used for the carbonation depth measurements (Figure 14).

In addition, the carbonation depth was measured from the staircase elements of the reference building. The carbonation depth was measured by drilling small holes to the concrete and applying the indicator liquid on the drilled holes (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Sampling locations in a deconstructed wall element, which – unlike a neighbouring element – was not destined for reuse (source: KTH).

Figure 15. Carbonation depth measurements from the drilled holes of the reference building (source: KTH).

3.3. Laboratory tests

No load tests were carried out for the elements in the Swedish pilot. The properties of the reused elements were only obtained from original documents and by in-situ investigation, i.e. sampling of cores. However, compressive strength, chloride content and hazardous and toxic substances were studied from the samples taken during in-situ investigation.

Compressive strength

Compressive strength was tested from the salvaged wall element (V7D) and floor element (P2). A total of 6 cores were used in the compressive strength assessment. The compressive strength testing was done according to EN 12390-3:2019 (2019) and the density was measured from the same samples according to EN 12390-7:2019 (2019).

Chloride content

The potential presence of chlorides, which can be a risk factor for corrosion and durability, was investigated on the salvaged wall and floor element. Chloride content was measured

at 3 depths from the same 3 core samples obtained from wall and slab elements that were also used in the carbonation depth measurements. The result of the test is a ratio of chlorides to cement weight. The chlorides were measured from a cylindrical sample of 10 mm from the core, and the content was determined by a potentiometric method (with an ion-selective electrode). The cement content was determined by titration with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and photometric measurement of the colour change from murexide indicator.

Hazardous substances

Hazardous substances were measured from the concrete of the wall and slab elements from the Drottninghög donor building. A total of four samples were investigated. The occurrence of hazardous substances was measured with a method that is referred to as 'Bygg-IS-1' (ALS, 2024) that relies on the use of inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The tested substances are arsenic, barium, cadmium, cobalt, chrome, copper, mercury, nickel, lead, vanadium, and zinc. The accuracy of the method (i.e. reporting limit) for the 11 tested substances is given in the report along with the results, and more information can be found in ALS (2024).

3.4. Results

Cover depth of reinforcement

GPR measurements of rebar cover depth are summarized with a histogram of all GPR measurements for the apartment in the examined building. Measurements were taken from the floor, i.e. top of the slab (Figure 16). As can be seen, the estimated depth of rebars is mostly around 15 cm, measured from the top of the concrete layer. These measurements align with the drawings of precast slabs. However, the reuse pilot had no requirements for the cover depth, as it was a temporary building.

The locations of reinforcements in the wall elements and the floor elements of one apartment of the reference building were found using GPR (Figure 17). The edge reinforcement for precast walls could not be detected, but some reinforcement such as the lifting hooks were detected. The probable reason for not detecting the edge reinforcement, which is positioned only 2–3 cm from the edge, is that the GPR device could not pass them close enough. Since no other rebars were detected for walls, it was decided to continue the scan for the rest of the walls with a quick horizontal and vertical scan for rebars, and to make more complete and detailed scans of the floors. The assumptions and findings from the scan of the walls and floors were confirmed with the drawings. Histograms for precast walls were not produced.

Figure 16. Histogram of cover depth measurements from slab elements in the apartment of the reference building.

Figure 17. Horizontal radargram of wall element at height of 2 meters from the floor.

Some benefits of using GPR were:

- Investigate the presence, location, and depth of rebars;
- It is a non-destructive test method that required a couple of hours for scanning an entire apartment;
- If the measurements are taken at greater distances, as usually done in practice, the time for taking measurements can be reduced;
- The thickness of elements can be estimated, e.g., slabs were around 18–20 cm and walls around 15 cm. The slight variation was due to different types of flooring between slabs (e.g. tiles, parquet, linoleum);
- GPR measurements were compared and confirmed by the drawings, and on-site measurements (e.g. thickness of walls);
- GPR cannot be used to accurately estimate the diameter of rebars;
- No anomalies were detected by the GPR, except when identifying lifting hooks, and voids for pipes which are part of the precast elements.

Carbonation depth

The carbonation depth is greater on one side of the floor slabs up to 62 mm (Table 8), potentially because the painted bottom surface of the slab has been more exposed to indoor air than the top surface, which has been covered with tiles or a parquet. The wall element has significantly lower carbonation depth than the slab elements.

Table 8. Mean value of carbonation depth measurements from slab and wall elements.

Sample (element type)	Surface of the sample	Carbonation depth [mm]
4 (slab)	side 1	38
	side 2	52
7 (wall)	side 1	4
	side 2	7
10 (slab)	side 1	36
	side 2	62

Compressive strength

The evaluated compressive strength class of the wall and slab elements from the Drottninghög donor is C35/45 (Table 9). This is two classes higher than the original compressive strength class C25/30.

Table 9. Compressive strength result of core samples from wall and slab elements.

Sample (element type)	Compressive strength, f_c [MPa]
1 (wall)	56.3
3 (wall)	51.0
5 (slab)	56.4
6 (slab)	44.0
8 (wall)	44.1
9 (slab)	41.4

Chloride content

Overall, the chloride content is low (Table 10). The maximum chloride content is 0.04 % of the cement weight.

Table 10. Chloride content measurements from slab and wall elements.

Sample (element type)	Surface of the sample	Chloride depth [mm]	Chloride/Cement [Weight-%]	Cement content [Weight-%]
4 (slab)	side 1	0-10	<0.01	20.4
	middle	70-80	<0.01	16.1
	side 2	0-10	<0.01	13.6
7 (wall)	side 1	0-10	0.03	18.2
	middle	85-95	<0.01	21.4
	side 2	0-10	0.03	23.1
10 (slab)	side 1	0-10	0.04	16.8
	middle	85-95	0.02	20.5
	side 2	0-10	0.02	25.2

Hazardous substances

The results of the measurements of hazardous substances are shown in Table 11. Some possible sources of contamination could be the raw materials or manufacturing processes or even other materials of the building components.

As can be seen, all measured results are below 100 ppm. The most restrictive green certification standards, such as 'Cradle to Cradle', 'Declare' and the 'Living Building Challenge' require reporting values for most chemical substances within the 1000 ppm or 100 ppm. For instance, the basic 'Declare' or 'LBC Red List approved' labels could be achieved for reused precast concrete elements. The 'LBC Red List approved' requires disclosure up to 99 % of ingredients present in the product. Moreover, reuse of these precast elements could potentially prevent the diffusion of hazardous substances, whereas their crushing could release these substances.

Table 11. Results of material analysis on samples from wall and slab elements. *) Limit of reporting (LOR) is the lowest concentration that can be detected with acceptable precision and accuracy. The values could be affected by dilution, limited number of samples used, or low dry matter content.

Substance	Unit	Sample				LOR*
		B1 (wall)	B2 (wall)	B4 (slab)	B5 (slab)	
As, arsenic	mg/kg	7.5	6.5	6.38	6.09	0.500
Ba, barium	mg/kg	20.2	17.8	20.5	21.1	1.000
CD, cadmium	mg/kg	<0.100	<0.100	0.17	0.125	0.100
Co, cobalt	mg/kg	3	3.26	3.52	3.07	0.100
Cr, chrome	mg/kg	13.6	11.3	14.4	13.4	0.200
Cu, copper	mg/kg	7.49	7.73	11.4	9.03	0.300
Hg, mercury	mg/kg	<0.200	<0.200	<0.200	<0.200	0.200
Ni, nickel	mg/kg	9.02	7.7	9.08	8.37	5.000
Pb, lead	mg/kg	5.43	5.68	8.67	8.52	1.000
V, vanadium	mg/kg	18.1	19.5	19.2	17.1	0.200
Zn, zinc	mg/kg	41.1	45.5	70	61.9	1.000

4. The Netherlands

4.1. Donor building

The donor building for the Dutch pilot project was an office building named Prinsenhof, located in Arnhem and built in 1988. The building consists of two wings, one with nine floors and the other with five floors (Figure 18). The wings are connected by a core that contains a staircase. The structure consists fully of precast concrete elements. The structure of both wings is created by hollow-core slabs spanning 13 meters between load-bearing precast facade elements. In total, 356 facade elements and 470 hollow-core slabs were used in the building.

Figure 18. Prinsenhof donor building in the Netherlands (source: Cementonline.nl).

The first round of information about the donor building and its elements was found through an archival study and a visit to the site. Through the archival study, several documents were found, such as the structural drawings of connections, section and plan drawings, shop drawings of precast concrete elements, and structural drawings and calculations of the elements and building. The documents formed the base of knowledge and will determine, together with the future use of the elements, what additional information (and thus testing) will be required. For example, the shop drawings give insight into the elements themselves, including the concrete type used and the presence of reinforcement (Figure 19 and Figure 20).

Figure 19. Technical drawing of a facade element (source: Hurks beton b.v.).

Figure 20. Technical drawing of a hollow-core slab (source: Dycore b.v.).

4.2. In-situ investigation

The in-situ investigation was planned according to the available information and considered reuse, and thus deconstruction rather than demolition. The following properties were studied in-situ: measurements, connections and material layers of floors. In addition, samples were taken for testing compressive strength of concrete and surveying hazardous and toxic substances during in-situ investigation. Both non-destructive and destructive methods were used.

Visual inspection

Visual inspection of the elements in the donor building was performed in multiple stages. The first was done when the building was determined to be deconstructed. After internal stripping, i.e. removing the non-structural materials, the elements were inspected again. In addition, the elements were inspected when they were deconstructed and were thus fully visible. Further visual investigation was also performed when the elements were transported. The cores drilled from the hollow-core slabs were also inspected visually to confirm the material layers in the floor structure. This led to the consideration of reusing the hollow-core slabs with existing layers, such as the structural topping and the screed layer.

Measurements

The dimensions of the elements were measured by using simple measuring tools. In addition, a 3D laser scan was taken from individual locations to create a point cloud (Figure 21). The point cloud was then used to verify the dimensions of the original drawings. Also, a BIM model was created.

Figure 21. Point cloud scans of Prinsenhof (source: unit2build b.v.).

Cover depth and diameter of reinforcement

The presence of reinforcement was investigated by using electromagnetic scanning with Ferroscan and GPR. As part of a master's thesis project (Donkervoort, 2024), two elements were tested to check the reinforcement on structural drawings. The amount, location (cover depth) and diameter of the reinforcement were obtained. The results were, however, ensured by local destructive testing. The concrete was removed with the help of water-

jetting, and the location and diameter could be measured. This will be used as a starting point to determine how many, which types of tests and the locations of the tests are needed for the new structure. The water-jetting also served as a test to consider if this could be a valid deconstruction method.

4.3. Laboratory tests

The performed laboratory tests included: bond between hollow-core slab and structural topping, presence of reinforcement in facade elements, compressive strength tests on cores from hollow-core slabs, bending test on hollow-core slabs and surveying hazardous and toxic substances.

Compressive strength

The compressive strength was evaluated from cores drilled from hollow-core slabs. A total of 4 cores were drilled and 3 of them were tested according to EN 13791:2019 (2019) and EN 1990 appendix D (2002). The fourth core was rejected, as it did not fulfil the requirements for the test because of cracking (Figure 22). The cores were drilled from two different locations on the fourth floor. The amount of compressive strength tests for facade elements remains to be determined.

Figure 22. Rejected core sample from hollow-core slab (source: Nebest b.v.).

Bond strength

To test the bond strength, three types of tests were performed and a fourth is planned. The first test performed was the pull-off test, as described in EN 13892-8 (2004). These tests were done twice, because the first series was not successful (the bond of the epoxy failed, and not the interface). The second series resulted in 20 successful tests. The second and third tests were splitting tests. The second test consisted of 32 tests and it was performed

deviating from the norm: cylinders were drilled on which the splitting test was performed where the force acts on the interface rather than the whole length of the cylinder. For the third test, 18 experiments were performed according to EN 12390-6, where the force acted on the whole length of the cylinder. The difference between the different testing methods will be analysed. The fourth test is still to be performed, this entails 12 shear tests. No norms were available and thus, this will be based on other literature.

Load tests

Two hollow-core slabs were sawn to a length of 7 meters to perform a three-point bending test by the original manufacturer, Dycore b.v. One of the slabs had 8 prestressed strands, while the other had 11 prestressed strands. The slabs were tested with the structural topping attached, as this is likely to be how they will be reused. Important to note is that one of the slabs had wooden strips cast in the structural topping (Figure 23); this limits the force transfer due to the lower compressive strength of wood. The wooden strips served as mounting points for roof elements, so are only present on the floor elements in the roof.

Figure 23. Wooden strips cast into the structural topping in the tested hollow-core slab (source: Dycore b.v.).

Hazardous substances

The presence of hazardous substances was studied in the donor building; mainly the occurrence of Chromium VI and asbestos. The investigation was performed according to Arbeidsomstandighedenwet (2023) and Asbestverwijderingsbesluit (2005). First, the

structural building plans were studied to find any indication of the use of these substances. Then, spot checks were performed in the building itself.

Influence of outdoor storage

There is an ongoing discussion to test the influence of storing precast concrete elements designed for an indoor environment in an outside environment. In non-freezing climates, this would mainly affect the corrosion rate of the reinforcement.

4.4. Results

Visual inspection and measurements

The visual inspection did not show considerable deviations or defects.

Cover depth and diameter of reinforcement

The reinforcement was found to match the original drawings. However, no reinforcement in the corbels of the facade elements was found in the original documents, but the presence was ensured by destructive testing. The location and size were thus ensured as well.

Compressive strength

The results of the compressive strength tests on the cores gave relative high values, 79.8 MPa, 88.1 MPa and 91.8 MPa. However, as only three cores were tested, a high deviation can be expected, and not all standards allow for working with only three samples. The standards EN 13791:2019 (2019) and EN 1990 (2002) appendix D allow for using only three samples, but this limits the strength-class substantially, to C50/60. This means that it would be beneficial to perform additional compressive strength tests.

Bond test

The bond strength tests between the hollow-core slabs and structural topping are currently ongoing. Therefore, no results are yet available.

Load tests

The bending moments achieved in the load tests were either 127 % of the calculated value (the slab with 8 prestressed strands and wooden strips in the topping) or 94 % (the slab with 11 prestressed strands). The calculations were based on the characteristic values gotten from the compressive strength testing. For the slab with the wooden strips, it was considered that the structural topping was not present as the wood would compress under tension. Thus, the slab was calculated as if there is not topping present. In reality, the strips transferred more forces than expected, and this is considered the reason for the underestimation of the bending moment.

Hazardous substances

Examining the drawings suggested possible presence of asbestos levelling blocks underneath the facade elements. After an in-situ investigation, it was determined they were not present. However, spot checks detected asbestos under each of the parapet elements as a levelling block. It was removed before deconstruction according to Asbestverwijderingsbesluit (2005).

5. Germany

5.1. Donor building

The German donor building was an apartment building in Hohenmölsen made of prefabricated reinforced concrete elements based on the 'P-Halle' (also known as 'IW 64') precast system from the German Democratic Republic (GDR) era (Figure 24). The elements were manufactured and assembled in the early 1980s.

Figure 24. Elevation drawing of the German donor building 'P-Halle' series (left, source: BBSR) and a photo of the building before partial deconstruction (right, © BTU).

The 'P-Halle' type series - like all prefabricated blocks of flats in the DDR - is based on the principle of cross-wall construction, i.e. the vertical loads from floors and traffic are only transferred via the internal transverse walls. The building is braced by the internal walls of the stairwell, the transverse walls and the floor slabs. Longitudinal exterior walls are designed as a self-supporting facade. In the donor building 'P-Halle', they are made of lightweight concrete. The gable walls are structurally reinforced. The basis of this construction type is a 1200 mm grid, which results in the following main dimensions:

- Building depth (system width): 9.6m (4.8m + 4.8m),
- Segment length (system length): 16.8m (3.6m + 3.6m + 2.4m + 3.6m + 3.6m),
- Ceiling spans: 2.4m + 3.6m,
- Floor height (structural frame) basement: 2.4m,
- Floor height (structural frame)-standard: 2.8m (2.65m + 0.14m thick floor slab).

The properties of the concrete elements installed in the donor building type 'P-Halle' were drawn from the old project planning documents from '*VEB Hochbauprojektierung Halle*' (VEB [Nationally owned enterprise] building construction project planning *Halle*). The documents were found in the special archives of Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development (BBSR) for buildings in the GDR.

The following elements are intended for reuse: 4 types of external wall elements, 3 types of load-bearing internal wall elements and 2 types of floor slabs.

The external wall elements have a thickness of 290 mm and are made of lightweight concrete with porous structure and a bulk density of 1250–1300 kg/m³. According to the project planning catalogue, they have a concrete quality of B 50 (compressive strength 5–8 MPa according to IEMB (2000), modulus of elasticity 12,2 GPa) in accordance with the GDR standards TGL 0–1047:1963–03 (1963) and TGL 1048:1963–04 (1963).

The load-bearing and bracing interior walls are made of concrete B 160 (compressive strength is 11 MPa and the modulus of elasticity is 23 GPa) with a bulk density of 2250 kg/m³. The thickness of the elements is generally 150 mm, while the height is 2635 mm and the length is 4810 mm (Figure 25). The elements with door openings are fitted with steel frames, so the door leaves may be attached.

The floor slabs are made of concrete class of B 225 (according to the project planning catalogue) with a bulk density of 2400 kg/m³, compressive strength of 22.7 MPa and modulus of elasticity of 27 GPa according to TGL 0–1047 (1963). The elements have a thickness of 140 mm, width of 2400 mm and length of either 2400 mm (D24) or 3600 mm (D36). The bottom of the panels is reinforced.

Figure 25. Deconstructed and partially tested elements Otto-Nuschke-Straße 9–14, 06679 Hohenmölsen: external walls (AW A – AW D), load-bearing interior walls (IW, IWT, IW2T) and floor slabs DE36 and DE24 (source: BTU).

5.2. In-situ investigation

The investigations are based on the decision-making methodology for the reuse of concrete elements (Mettke, 1995), which has been tested and tried in earlier pilots, and which is reflected in the local guideline of the state of Brandenburg (Land Brandenburg, 2012). The guideline is based on the Brandenburg Building Code (BbgBO, 2023). As there are not yet any recognised rules of technology for reused concrete elements, a proof of usability must be submitted for approval in individual cases – in accordance with § 20 BbgBO – to the highest building supervisory authority.

The following investigations were carried out in the donor building before the deconstruction:

- Visual inspection with the aid of a building condition catalogue with special attention to cracks, their location and depth, deformations, spalling on the surface, exposed reinforcement, etc.
- Metrological assessment
 - Compressive strength of concrete
 - Cover depth of reinforcement
 - Non-destructive carbonation depth testing
- Computational and experimental verification
 - Load-bearing capacity or serviceability of the concrete elements subject to bending stress, i.e. the floor slabs.

The following investigations were carried out after the deconstruction of the concrete elements on the interim storage area:

- Visual inspection with special attention to edge spalling and/or new cracks.
- Measuring assessments for:
 - Repeated random testing of concrete compressive strength: non-destructive testing using rebound hammer and selective testing on drill cores
 - Depth of carbonation on drill cores

Cover depth and diameter of reinforcement

The location, cover depth and diameter of reinforcement were determined from 12 floor slabs (Figure 26). Electromagnetic scanning with a non-destructive test device Hilti Ferroskan RV 10 was performed.

Figure 26. Non-destructive testing of the location and diameter of slab reinforcement (excerpt from digitally recorded measurement results of the longitudinal and transverse reinforcement) (source: BTU).

Compressive strength

The rebound hammer test for evaluating the compressive strength was done by using a Schmidt-Hammer Type N/NR model. A total of 27 concrete elements were tested (Figure 27):

- 6 floor slabs DE36 (length 3.6 m)
- 11 interior wall elements
- 10 exterior wall elements.

Figure 27. In-situ rebound hammer concrete strength test (source: BTU).

Hazardous substances

The following obligations regarding hazardous substance apply on any dismantling works:

- Separation of waste for recycling in accordance with § 9 KrWG (2020) and § 8 GewAbfV (2022)
- Obligation to properly and harmlessly recycle waste in accordance with § 7 KrWG
- Obligation to dispose of non-recycled waste in a manner compatible with the common good in accordance with § 15 KrWG.

The donor building was surveyed accordingly for possible hazardous substances before deconstruction.

5.3. Laboratory tests & structural analysis

Compressive strength

Compressive strength of elements was tested in-situ with a rebound hammer and in laboratory with drilled cores with a diameter of 100 mm. A total of 21 cores were taken from the elements (6 cores from exterior walls, 4 cores from interior walls and 11 cores from floor

slabs) for the compressive strength testing (Figure 28). The sampling and testing were done according to EN 12504-1 (2021).

In addition, the modulus of elasticity was determined from three core samples taken from the floor slabs. The diameter of the cores for the testing was 50 mm. The modulus of elasticity was determined according to EN 12390-13 (2021).

The core samples were sent to the laboratory, where the compressive strength testing and was done according to EN 12390-13 (2021). The test reports were written with minimum specifications according to Zimmer et al. (2021).

Figure 28. Collection of drill cores from ceiling slabs (source: BTU).

Carbonation depth

Carbonation depth was measured in-situ from each core sample after drilling. A total of 23 cores were tested. The carbonation depth was determined by using phenolphthalein indicator liquid, which was sprayed on concrete surface of the cores, like in the Finnish pilot. The depth was measured with a tape measure (Figure 29).

Figure 29. Determination of the carbonation depth of the concrete cores (source: BTU).

Structural analysis

Due to the lack of data sheets for the floor slabs installed in the donor building, ReCreate partner P. Jähne Ingenieurbüro GmbH calculated their load-bearing capacity using the software BauStatik according to the results from in-situ and laboratory tests.

5.4. Results

Visual inspection

The visual inspection in-situ did not reveal any defects in the elements that would influence their reuse. However, after deconstruction, minor defects, such as spalling of concrete, was found (Figure 30). These defects do not have an effect on the structural capacity and the elements can be repaired before reuse.

Figure 30. Defects found in the elements at the on-site temporary storage: adhering joint mortar on outer walls, spalling concrete, edge damage. (source: BTU).

Cover depth and diameter of reinforcement

The measured reinforcement diameters of floor slab elements vary. The diameter of 6 mm for transverse reinforcement in a depth of 29 mm was found for the shorter slab elements by using Ferroskan. However, the result was verified by crumbling three elements and measuring the diameter. The transverse reinforcement was then found to be 8 mm. The longitudinal reinforcement was found to be 10 mm in a depth of 20 mm, which corresponds to the results of Ferroskan. The longer slab elements (3.6 m) have a longitudinal reinforcement of \varnothing 10 mm.

Carbonation depth

The carbonation depths in the elements (exterior walls, interior walls and floor slabs) are so low that they cannot be detected (Figure 29), and the carbonation front has not reached the reinforcement. Therefore, there is no risk of corrosion.

Compressive strength

The compressive strength class evaluated from the rebound hammer results vary between C20/25 and C35/45 (Figure 31).

Rebound values																
Protocol no.	2		2		1		2		1		2		2		2	
Test point	Test area AWa		Test area AWb		Prüfbereich AWc		Prüfbereich AWd		Prüfbereich IW		Prüfbereich IW4		Prüfbereich IW4		Prüfbereich IWS	
	measuring point (MP)	measuring point (MP)	MP1	MP2	MP1	MP2	MP1	MP2	MP1	MP2	MP1	MP2	MP1	MP2	MP1	MP2
1	41	40	40	40	40	45	41	44	45	44	42	42	40	42	47	43
2	45	42	40	39	42	44	40	44	44	42	44	42	44	42	43	47
3	44	44	38	38	46	47	40	44	42	48	42	42	41	40	49	38
4	44	46	40	37	44	43	46	45	42	46	45	43	45	42	44	47
5	44	43	40	38	48	44	45	45	44	46	42	43	43	41	44	47
6	42	44	40	39	43	43	44	47	42	44	41	43	42	45	45	47
7	42	42	40	37	45	40	46	42	46	46	42	43	39	42	45	47
8	44	42	39	38	43	45	43	42	50	43	46	42	39	40	47	47
9	40	45	39	38	44	39	43	41	48	43	42	41	43	40	46	46
MEDIAN	44	43	40	38	44	44	43	44	44	44	42	42	42	42	45	47
MEDIAN minMS	43		38		44		43		44		42		42		45	44
MEDIAN ges	43.5		39		44		44		44		42		42		47	44
Value lowest	40		36		39		40		42		41		39		38	41
	C30/37	C30/37	C25/30	C25/30	C35/45	C30/37	C30/37	C30/37	C35/45	C30/37	C30/37	C25/30	C30/37	C25/30	C35/45	C35/45
Method 1 new	C30/37	C30/37	C20/25	C25/30	C30/37	C30/37	C30/37	C30/37	C30/37	C30/37	C25/30	C25/30	C30/37	C25/30	C35/45	C30/37

Arrangement of the test points at a measuring point on the structural elements

Figure 31. Evaluation of the of the compressive strength based on rebound hammer tests (excerpt) (source: BTU).

In summary, the following can be concluded for the determination of the concrete compressive strength using a rebound hammer:

- exterior wall (type AW C): 30/37
- interior wall (type IW C): 25/30 to C 35/45
- floor slab (3.6 m length): C 30/37

The compressive strength from laboratory tests shows the following results (average value): exterior walls 23.5 MPa, interior walls 40.8 MPa, floor slabs 3.6 m 43.3 MPa, floor slabs 2.4 m 41.4MPa. The compressive strength of the elements has increased so that it has become on average about 2–4 times the design value typical to these kinds of elements. (Table 12) However, the exact original design value for compressive strength of the elements from the donor building are not known.

The modulus of elasticity tested from the cores from floor slabs vary according to the slab length. The slabs of 2.4 m have an average value of 26.5 GPa, and the slabs of 3.6 m vary between 20.7 GPa and 25.8 GPa.

Hazardous substances

Asbestos-containing polymer-bound mastic (trade name 'Morinol') was found in the joints of the outer wall (Figure 32). It was used to seal the joints between the concrete elements against the effects of the weather. The removal of the Morinol and its proper disposal was subcontracted to an approved specialist company for asbestos removal and disposal, in accordance with the applicable law TRGS 519. The removal was carried out before deconstruction in accordance with the guideline DGUV Information 201-012 (2021). The waste was then packaged and disposed of properly. No other hazardous substances were found.

Table 12. Comparison of compressive strength and compressive strength class of concrete of elements for reuse according to old project planning catalogues, in-situ non-destructive testing, and laboratory tests of drill cores. Notes: n = number of cores (core testing), l = number of measuring points (rebound hammer test).

Type of element	Unit	reference/method of testing and corresponding strength class				trend (+/0/-)	compared with rebound hammer tests
		data sheet	strength class	core testing	strength class		
floor slabs (DE)	MPa (N/m ²)	22,7	C16/20	46,4 (n=11)	C30/37 to C40/50,	+	C30/37 (i=6)
Exterior walls (AW)	MPa (N/m ²)	5-8	C8/12	23,5 (n=6)	C12/15 to C16/20	++	C30/37 (i=6)
interior walls (IW)	MPa (N/m ²)	11	C12/15	40,8 (n=4)	C30/37	+++	C25/30 to C35/45 (i=4)

Figure 32. Removed joint sealant from external wall element (source: BTU).

Structural analysis

Calculating the load-bearing capacity of floor slabs with a statics programme analysis (Figure 33) showed that the 3.6 m long floor slabs are sufficiently reinforced (with the Ø 10 mm longitudinal reinforcement bars) for the load-bearing capacity required in the planned reuse pilot. The 2.4 m long floor slabs were similarly found reusable, as the diameter of their reinforcement had been verified to be 8 mm by crumbling a sample of these elements, and not 6 mm as suggested by the Hilti Ferroskan investigation. Had the diameter been only 6 mm, the load-bearing capacity of the slabs would not have been sufficient.

Figure 33. A screen capture from structural analysis of the floor slab (DE 36).

6. Conclusions

Even though ReCreate's four pilot projects are in different countries and have different kind of donor buildings and salvaged elements, fairly similar tests were carried out in each case, both in-situ and in a laboratory. Nevertheless, some differences in the selected testing approaches and methods occur, which refers to differing testing requirements in different pilots and contexts.

In all, the reclaimed elements were found to be in a reusable condition in each pilot. The elements were inspected visually in several stages. The compressive strength of concrete was tested with different test methods. Also, reinforcements of elements were studied in each case. These are the relevant properties for reusing load-bearing concrete elements because they are needed to determine the structural capacity. In addition, to ensure the health of building users in reuse, harmful substances were surveyed from the donor buildings. The extent and the methods for studying them varied according to national practices.

In comparison to the original design values, the compressive strength of concrete has increased in each pilot. Plenty of coarse cement has been used in concrete structures previously, which decreases the rate of hardening. The compressive strength was studied with a rebound hammer and drilled cores. The results from the two methods are not similar. In general, the rebound hammer test underestimates the strength.

Also other properties, such as carbonation depth, concrete cover of reinforcement, presence of chlorides and protective pore ratio were tested with suitable methods, but not in all pilots. The importance of these tests depends on the new building, where the elements are reused, and the location of the salvaged elements in it (e.g. indoors/outdoors).

More generally, a harmonized testing procedure, which is the aim of future ReCreate deliverables D4.2 and D4.3, could decrease the risk of insufficient testing as well as over-testing in future deconstruction and reuse projects. The former might risk the health and safety of reuse, while the latter could incur unnecessary costs and so reduce the competitiveness of reuse against virgin materials.

References

ALS. (2020). *Bygg-IS-1 Grundämnen (II) i byggnadsmaterial, 7M HNO3 uppslutning*. https://www.alsglobal.se/paket/milj-1/avfall-och-byggnadsmaterial_36/grund-mnen_5/bygg-is-1-grund-mnen-ii-i-byggnadsmaterial-7m-hno3-uppslutning_17450

Arbetsomstandighedenwet - BWBR0010346 (2023).

Asbestverwijderingsbesluit BWBR0019316 (2005).

ASTM C856/C856M-20. (2020). *Standard Practice for Petrographic Examination of Hardened Concrete*. ASTM International.

BbgBO. (2023). Brandenburgische Bauordnung.

DGUV Information 201-012. (2021). Emissionsarme Verfahren nach TRGS 519 für Tätigkeiten an asbesthaltigen Materialien.

Donkervoort J. (2024) The reliability of non-destructive test methods used for measuring the rebar configuration applied in existing concrete elements and the improvement of these measurements to enhance the reliability.

EN 1168 + A3. (2012). *Precast concrete products. Hollow core slabs*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12390-3. (2019). *Testing hardened concrete - Part 3: Compressive strength of test specimens*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12390-6. (2009). *Testing hardened concrete - Part 6: Tensile splitting strength of test specimens*.

EN 12390-7. (2019). *Testing hardened concrete - Part 7: Density of hardened concrete*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12390-13. (2019) *Testing hardened concrete - Part 13: Determination of secant modulus elasticity in compression*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12504-1:2019 + AC:2020. (2021). *Testing concrete in structures. Part 1: Cored specimens. Taking, examining and testing in compression*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12504-2:2021. (2021). *Testing concrete in structures. Part 2: Non-destructive testing. Determination of rebound number*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 13791:2019. (2019). *Assessment of in-situ compressive strength in structures and precast concrete components*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 13892-8:2004 (2004). *Method of test for screed materials – part 8: Determination of bond strength*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 1542. (1999). *Products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures. Test methods. Measurement of bond strength by pull-off*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 1990. (2023). *Eurocode. Basis of structural and geotechnical design*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 1991. (2002). *Eurocode 1. Actions on structures*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 1992. (2023). *Eurocode 2. Design of concrete structures*. European Committee for Standardization.

GewAbfV (2022). *Regulation on the management of commercial municipal waste and certain construction and demolition waste (Commercial Waste Regulation - Gewerbeabfallverordnung -GewAbfV)*

IEMB. (2000). *Sanierungsgrundlagen Plattenbau, Tragverhalten von Außenwandelementen aus haufwerksporigem Leichtbeton nach TGL, Hrsg. IEMB, Institut für Erhaltung und Modernisierung von Bauwerken e.V. an der TU Berlin, Fraunhofer IRB Verlag,04/2000, p. 10.*

ISO 6892-1:2019. (2019). *Metallic materials. Tensile testing. Part 1: Method of test at room temperature*. International Organization for Standardization.

KrWG. (2020). *Act to Promote the Circular Economy and Ensure the Environmentally Friendly Management of Waste (Circular Economy Act - Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz - KrWG)*.

Land Brandenburg. (2012). *Wiederverwendung von Fertigteilen aus Beton, Stahl- und Spannbeton*.

Mettke. (1995). *Wiederverwendung von Bauelementen des Fertigteilbaus. Series Environmental Sciences Volume 5, Eberhard Blottner Verlag.*

RILEM CPC-18. (1988). *Measurement of hardened concrete carbonation depth*. RILEM Publications SARL.

RT 103501. (2022). *Haitalliset aineet rakennuksissa. Tutkijan ohje*. Rakennustieto.

SFS 4475. (1988). *Betoni. Pakkasekestävyys. Suojahuokossuhde*. Finnish Standards Association SFS. *Withdrawn*.

SFS 7508:2021. (2021). *Application of standard SFS-EN 13791 in Finland*. Finnish Standards Association SFS.

SS 137242. (1988). *Concrete testing - Hardened concrete - Depth of carbonation*. Swedish Institute for Standards.

TGL 0-1047:1963-03. (1963). *Bauwerke aus Beton. Projektierung. Ausführung*. GDR standard.

TGL 1048:1963-04. (1963). *Betonprüfungen*. GDR standard.

TGRS 519. (2022). *Asbest - Abbruch-, Sanierungs- oder Instandhaltungsarbeiten*. German technical rules for hazardous substances.

Vullings, M., Henschel C., Wijte, S.N.M., Huuhka, S., Salmio, E., Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Stenberg, E., Westerlind, H., & Dervishaj, A. (2024). *Real-life deconstruction pilots of the ReCreate project*. The ReCreate project.

Zimmer et al. (2021). *Handbuch der Betonprüfung, Prüfanleitungen und Beispiele*, 7th edition Verlag Bau+Technik GmbH.